

Appendix 1. Informants

Code	Last Name/ First Name	Workplace	Country	Sector	Position
R01	Alvarado Miquilena, Morella	Central University of Venezuela	Venezuela	University	Director
J01	Arenas, Zayira	HispanoPost	Venezuela	Native digital media	Editor
R02	Bolívar, Ligia	Dejusticia	Colombia	NGO	Fellow
J02	Cano, Fidel	El Espectador	Colombia	Media, national newspaper	Newspaper director
R03	Caprile, Mariana	Laboratory of Social Sciences (LACSO) and Venezuelan Observatory of Violence (OVV)	Venezuela	NGO	Project Coordinator
R04	Chávez, Nelly	Central American University José Simeón Cañas	El Salvador	University	Dean
J03	García Jiménez, Jorge Iván	El Tiempo	Colombia	Media, national newspaper	Editor
J04	Gil Gutiérrez, Juliana	El Colombiano	Colombia	Media, national newspaper	International journalist
R05	Hernández, Gustavo	Andres Bello Catholic University	Venezuela	University	Professor
J05	López, Liza	Historias que laten	Venezuela	Independent media	Editor
J06	Mayorca, Javier	Crímenes sin castigo	Venezuela	Independent media	journalist
R06	Méndiz Rojas, Heleny	Northern Catholic University	Chile	University	Researcher
J07	Mesa Rivera, María	Venezuela Migration Project / Revista Semana	Colombia	Media. Magazine	Journalist
J08	Mora, Aliss	Freelance journalist	Colombia	Independent media	Freelance journalist
R07	Páez Silva, Gustavo Alejandro	Los Andes University	Venezuela	University	Professor
R08	Quiroz, María Teresa	University of Lima	Perú	University	Director
R09	Ranzolin, Alexandra	Monteavila University	Venezuela	University	Dean
R10	Robayo, María Clara	Observatory of Venezuela of the Rosario University	Colombia	University	Director
R11	Ronderos, María Teresa	Independent Journalism Program, Open Society Foundations	Colombia	NGO	Director
J09	Salazar, Sania	Colombiacheck	Colombia	Native digital media	Journalist
J10	Sulbarán, Rafael David	El Pitazo	Colombia	Native digital media	Journalist

Nota: VE (Venezuela), CO (Colombia), CH (Chile), PE (Perú) ES (El Salvador).